

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES INC.

11th
ANNUAL
REPORT

for the year ended June 30, 1967

Magister Scriniarum.

Memoriae epistolarum libellorum Græcarum.

ANNUAL REPORT

for the year ended June 30, 1967

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

1028 Connecticut Ave., N.W., Washington, D. C. 20036

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

July 1, 1966 - June 30, 1967

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Director, Folger Shakespeare Library

¹ See footnote, page 5.

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Senior Staff Members

LEE E. GROVE, *Director of Publications*
LAURENCE B. HEILPRIN, *Physicist*⁴
ROBERT T. JORDAN, *Library Specialist*

¹ On June 17, 1967 Dr. Cole was elected to succeed Mr. Clapp as President of the Council, effective September 1, 1967.

² Professor Morse was elected to succeed President Coles as a Member of the Executive Committee, November 12, 1967.

³ On leave of absence, to serve as staff director of the National Advisory Commission on Libraries, to January 1, 1968.

⁴ Until January 31, 1967.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

The Year 1966-1967

During the year that ended June 30, 1967 the Council awarded a total of \$1,124,389 for the support of 38 projects. The amount of money was larger than in any except two other years since the Council's establishment, and the number of projects was as large or larger than in all but four years. One factor contributing to this result was that conditions which had previously hindered investigations in some areas were finally replaced. Specifically, in the field of library automation the Council made 14 grants last year in a total amount of \$549,835; none of these would have been made before computer print-out in lower as well as upper case type became a feasible actuality.

It is interesting to note, however, that the Council has found no less need for its assistance in the support of attempts to find solutions to library problems because of the great increase in the moneys available for this purpose to which attention was called in the preceding report in this series.¹ Indeed, the need seems to be at least as acute, if not even greater than in earlier years.

Projects commenced or continued with new funds during the years, as well as projects completed, are described in the pages that follow. Those that were still in progress from grants of previous years are only mentioned if, for example, a progress report is called to attention.

The scheme of arrangement used for the past eight years has (as may be seen from the Table of Contents) been abandoned in this report. The previous categorization of projects classified them under four headings— as concerned with bibliographic or physical access, with administrative factors or with planning. This arrangement has proved very useful and more closely approximated exclusiveness (i.e., placing the object classified exclusively in one category without overlapping into another) than any other tried. In the present report, however, it was desired to emphasize certain groupings of which the members would have been separated by the four-category arrangement. Specifically, the projects brought together in both Chapter II, Archives, and III, Automation, would have previously been scattered.

As the reflection of the activity of but a single year, the listing of topics presented in the Table of Contents suggests the complexity and diversity of the subject which forms the Council's assignment. The projects funded during the past

¹ X: 31. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports; in this case to the 10th Annual Report, page 31.

year were selected with great care; each, it is believed, will make a contribution, and some are of high interest and potentially great importance for the future of library work. But the search for solutions to the problems of libraries cannot—nor will—for that reason be diminished or neglected.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

August 1967

Projects Commenced or Completed 1966-1967

I. ARCHIVES

Access to archival collections A brief account of the Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives held in Washington in May 1966 with the National Archives of the United States serving as host, was presented in the previous annual report.² The Congress brought together leaders of the international archival community from 53 countries and every continent to discuss the general theme, "Archives for Scholarship: Encouraging Greater Ease of Access." From these discussions there resulted a series of resolutions designed to promote the maximum practicable freedom of scholarly access to archival and manuscript sources of history. To implement these resolutions the International Council appointed two committees of approximately 10 members each, and the Council this past year made a grant to assist their work.

The first committee is responsible for continuing the efforts of the Extraordinary Congress to facilitate scholarly access to archives with special emphasis on the shortening of periods of closure, creation of an international reader's card as a step in the direction of equal access regardless of nationality, and liberalization of microfilming policy to facilitate reproduction of entire series or archive groups and of documentation dealing with the history of foreign countries. The second committee is studying the most economical and efficient methods for the publication of archival sources, giving particular consideration to the potentialities of microfilm. It is expected that both committees will submit reports during the next International Archival Congress, to be held in Madrid in September 1968. M. Etienne Sabbe, President of the International Council and Archivist General of Belgium, is chairman of both committees.

Machine - indexing of archival and manuscript collections The custodians of archival and manuscript collections face increasingly the complex problem of retrieving information from the multiplicity of source materials in their care. Old methods of describing materials were adequate up to a point, but with the rapid increase in the number and size of these collections the old methods are no longer feasible. In 1940 the National Archives contained some 330,000 cubic feet of records

² X: 46. See also "Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives." *American Archivist* 30: 81-89, January 1967.

and had a staff of about 400 persons to service them. If the ratio of material to personnel had been maintained the staff would have had to be increased to more than 1200 by 1967. Actually it increased to a total of less than 500 persons. This then-and-now ratio of staff to materials is typical of archival and manuscript repositories. Simultaneously, however, the demands by scholars upon these institutions have increased. The methods used to serve the scholarly public a few decades ago are inadequate to the demands being made upon archivists and curators today.

These considerations underlay a grant made during the past year to the National Archives and Records Service for a project to develop and apply methods for preparing finding aids to archival and manuscript materials by computers. This will build on experience gained elsewhere, including the result of a program developed by the principal investigator, Mr. Frank G. Burke while associated with the Library of Congress.³ Preliminary soundings in more than 25 repositories have indicated the possibility of developing a program generally applicable to archival and manuscript collections and yet having sufficient flexibility to accommodate the problems peculiar to each. This project might therefore become the basis for a national or even an international system.

The early development of archival practices

Two of the best known epigraphs in Washington are those which are cut on the pedestals of the statues which flank the Pennsylvania Avenue entrance to the National Archives. These inscriptions — quotations with some adaption from Shakespeare and Confucius — are "What Is Past Is Prologue" and "Study the Past." While in the context the reference is plainly to the study of archival records, it can with equal propriety be taken to apply to the study of archival practices. However this may be, the Council has made a grant to the Society of American Archivists to assist Dr. Ernst Posner, Professor Emeritus of History and Archives Administration of the American University, to expedite the completion of his study of the archival practices of the ancient world from the days of Sumer to the end of the Roman Empire, 3000 B.C. to A.D. 565.

Dr. Posner is the author of *American State Archives*,⁴ the important report of a study conducted for the Society of American Archivists with assistance from the Council.⁵

Status of the National Archives

The National Archives of the United States, established by Act of Congress in 1934, existed as an independent agency until 1949. Since then it has functioned within the General Services Administration as the National Archives and Records Service. Because the

³ Frank G. Burke, "The application of automated techniques in the management and control of source materials." *American Archivist* 30: 255-78, April 1967.

⁴ University of Chicago Press, 1964.

⁵ VI: 36-7; IX: 11, 39, 48-51; X: 16.

activities of this agency (whose responsibilities extend to archives, records management, historical publications and the publication of the *Federal Register* as well as to administration of Presidential libraries) so profoundly affect historical studies both currently and for the indefinite future, the historical associations have been concerned lest this loss of independence impair the effectiveness of its service. In December 1966 the Council of the American Historical Association established a committee to study the question jointly with the Society of American Archivists and the Organization of American Historians. The Council has made a small grant to assist this inquiry.

II. AUTOMATION

Project Released from the restriction of an exclusively upper-
MARC case font of type upon their output, the application of computers to the problems of libraries could at long last go forward with assurance and rapidity. The breakthrough was signalled in August 1964 when the first issue of the *Index Medicus* was printed under computer control in both upper and lower case type. Presuming upon this success, and in furtherance of its belief that meaningful automation of library activities is dependent upon the availability of bibliographic data in standardized machine-readable form, the Council had already commissioned a preliminary and subsequently a fuller study of the procedures for converting the bibliographic data on Library of Congress printed catalog cards to a machine-readable record that would permit automatic reproduction of such data either as catalog cards, for a book-format catalog or for other uses such as accession-lists, shelf-lists, book-cards, book-pockets, and book-labels. The resulting report by Lawrence F. Buckland of Inforonics, Inc., which also appeared in August 1964,⁶ was several times reprinted in the following year. Its wide distribution and easy comprehensibility may be supposed to have contributed to the understanding of the problems of computer-based library automation and thus to subsequent developments. In a further attempt to prepare the way, the Council at this time commissioned a study of the problem of making computers learn the Library of Congress' filing rules. This eventuated in a report by William R. Nugent, also of Inforonics, Inc.⁷

⁶ Lawrence F. Buckland, *The Recording of Library of Congress Bibliographical Data in Machine Form*. Maynard, Massachusetts: Inforonics, Inc., 1964. Revised, February 1965. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1965. 54 p.

⁷ William R. Nugent, *The Mechanization of the Filing Rules for the Dictionary Catalogs of the Library of Congress*. Maynard, Massachusetts: Inforonics, Inc., 1966. 32 p. In press as an article for the Fall 1967 issue of *Library Resources and Technical Services*.

By the fall of 1965, in consequence, conditions were at last ripe for an effort to fashion the arrangements for making bibliographic information regarding current publications — of the kind used by most libraries in their daily operations — available in standardized machine-readable form. With the encouragement of the Council and of the Automation Committee of the Association of Research Libraries, the Library of Congress designed Project MARC (Machine-Readable Catalog), a program intended to result in the distribution, beginning in the fall of 1966, of cataloging information in machine-readable form to a group of participating libraries. Essential to the project was a proposed review designed to inform the Library regarding the experiences of the participating libraries resulting from the demonstration. It was expected that the project would be completed in early 1967.⁸

In spite of many obstacles the Library of Congress commenced distribution of magnetic tapes containing cataloging information regarding current publications to the participating libraries in the fall of 1966,⁹ and at about the same time contracted for review of their experience. When the terminal date for the project arrived, however, the Library found the demand for its uninterrupted continuance so insistent that it has continued it without break. However, the materials from which the final report of the project were to have been prepared had accumulated in such quantity that a special arrangement was needed to reduce them to a publishable report. Accordingly, the Council has made a subsidiary grant to the Library to enable it to expedite the report of the MARC experiment with a view to its issuance during 1967.

The Council has assisted in still another problem connected with the birththroes of the distribution of cataloging information in machine-readable form. Libraries desirous of acquiring the MARC computer tapes are willing to pay for them, but normal practice requires the Library of Congress to pay for the tapes from its own operating funds while the receipts from sales would revert to the U.S. Treasury. To make it possible to apply receipts to the cost of the tapes the Council has made a small grant to enable the Library of Congress to establish a revolving fund.

New England Board of Higher Education The prospect afforded by Project MARC, that cataloging information in machine-readable form might be available in the foreseeable future, made it possible to go forward along lines heretofore blocked. One of these was in planning a regional computer-based library processing center. The libraries of the state-supported universities of the six New England states united

⁸ X: 29-30, 41-2.

⁹ Library of Congress. Information Systems Office: *A Preliminary Report on the MARC (Machine-Readable-Cataloging) Pilot Project*. Washington, 1966. 101 p., 27 cm.

"Test tapes for MARC Project shipped." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 25: 683-4, November 3, 1966.

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A REGIONAL COMPUTER-BASED PROCESSING CENTER is being planned to serve the libraries of six state-supported universities united under the New England Board of Higher Education. Pictured are: 1, Goodell Library, Amherst campus of the University of Massachusetts; 2, Ezekiel Dimond Library, University of New Hampshire; 3, University of Rhode Island Library; 4, Guy W. Bailey Memorial Library, University of Vermont; 5, Wilbur Cross Library, University of Connecticut; 6, Raymond H. Fogler Library, University of Maine.

under the New England Board of Higher Education had been discussing the possibility of such a center with the Council for several years, but only in 1966 did conditions justify going ahead. In July 1966 a first grant was made to the Board to enable it to contract for the design of a center which would supply cataloging and other book-processing information and services to the six libraries, creating in the process a file which would rapidly become a union catalog of these libraries and of many others that might join the system. It was stipulated that the center should maintain complete compatibility with the MARC project, since it was presumed that it would eventually secure much of its information from the Library of Congress.¹⁰

The design, prepared by Inforonics, Inc., was sufficiently advanced by January 1967 to permit implementation to begin. In that month the Council made a second grant to the Board, to enable it to procure computer programs for establishing the central file. Before the end of the year the Council made still a third grant, to enable the Board to commission programs for searching the file, to extend technical processing activities to acquisitions, and to begin a pilot operation. Prior to the start of this pilot operation a record is to be made of the present costs to the six libraries for processing their books; such a record is expected to be useful for evaluative purposes later.

Project Intrex In a press release dated January 16, 1964, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology announced that Dr. Carl F. J. Overhage, who had been director of its Lincoln Laboratory for the previous seven years, would on the 1st of July following become a professor in the School of Engineering with the assignment of establishing the bases on which the technical library of the future might be modeled, with the ultimate objective of designing a library of engineering and science that could be put into operation at M.I.T. between 1970 and 1975. This announcement was of more than usual interest to the Council, which immediately made collaborative overtures to Dr. Overhage. After some months of initial exploration of the problems, he organized at Woods Hole, in August-September 1965, a five-week conference to explore the problems of information exchange looking to the design of an investigation. A report of the conference, presenting the main elements of the design, was promptly published.¹¹

In June 1966 the Institute approached the Council for major support of what had come to be known as Project Intrex (*Information*

¹⁰ "Regional library computer center under study." *Higher Education in New England* (Winchester, Mass.: New England Board of Higher Education) 10:3: 1, 7, Autumn 1966.

Donald E. Vincent, "New England state university libraries' regional processing center." *American Library Association: ALA Bulletin* 61: 672-3, June 1967.

¹¹ Carl F. J. Overhage and R. Joyce Harms, eds.: *Intrex. Report of a Planning Conference on Information Transfer Experiments*. Cambridge, Massachusetts and London, England: The M.I.T. Press, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, [c. 1965]. 276 p.

Transfer Experiments). Although the Council could not meet the entire request, in January 1967 it made a substantial grant to enable the Institute to investigate, for one year beginning March 1, 1967, the possibilities for improving the arrangements for access by users to printed text. Experiments with real library users in actual working situations are planned, using a variety of new techniques for full-text access to determine their economic feasibility and degree to which they satisfy user requirements. Examples of promising technologies include the following: graphic storage of full-text in microfilm or other reduced format; automatic selection through a time-shared computer utility; transmission of a scanned-image electrical signal over a communication network and display and/or reproduction in full size or microform for temporary and/or permanent retention by the user; digital storage of encoded full-text in massive random-access storage; selection and transmission through a time-shared computer system with display and/or reproduction for use through remote computer terminals. The research and development efforts are under the direction of Professor J. Francis Reintjes, director of the Institute's Electronics Systems Laboratory.

Standards for converting bibliographic information to machine-readable form

The Buckland report of 1964 on the conversion of Library of Congress cataloging data to machine-readable form was an important initial attack on the "conversion problem." This was carried forward by the Library of Congress itself in the source of the MARC project under the direction of Mrs. Henriette Avram, Assistant Coordinator in the Information Systems Office, Library of Congress. Meanwhile the Sectional Committee on Standards in Library work and Documentation of the United States of America Standards Institute (formerly the American Standards Association) assigned the problem of a standard of conversion to one of its subcommittees, and the Council, jointly with the National Science Foundation, funded a study looking toward the development of a national (or even international) standard in this matter, so fundamental for the efficient application of computers to library work. Appropriately, Mrs. Avram is chairman and Mr. Buckland a member of this subcommittee. A further report of this project is presented below in the discussion of testing and standardization.

The Journal of Library Automation

Indicative of the importance that automation has come to assume in the field of library work is the establishment in 1966 of an Information Science and Automation Division within the American Library Association. A principal need of the new Division is for a journal which can select and publish from the large and growing literature of automation those articles which would be useful to its members. The Council has consequently made a grant to assist it to publish a quarterly *Journal of Library Automation*, which is expected to become self-supporting at the end of three years. Mr. Frederick G. Kilgour, Director of the Ohio College Library Center

and formerly Associate Librarian of Yale University, who has contributed significantly to developments in the field, has accepted the editorship.

A computer center for five District of Columbia university libraries

Within the borders of the District of Columbia are five universities banded together in the Consortium of Universities of Washington, D. C. They include American University, Catholic University, Georgetown University, George Washington University, and Howard University. Within the Consortium, in turn, the libraries of these institutions collaborate in an Interuniversity Library Council in such efforts as the compilation of a union list of serials of the five libraries, and in the establishment of an interlibrary delivery service. Concurrently, the libraries have been studying how data processing and computer techniques might help them individually to improve their operations and services. A felt need, however, was an answer to the question whether a computer center in the service of all five libraries might not be more effective than any such services which the libraries might be able to procure separately. To assist in securing an answer to this question the Council has made a grant to Georgetown University to commission a study, by a nationally recognized expert, Dr. Ralph H. Parker, Director of Libraries at the University of Missouri, of the alternatives involved.

A manual of systems design for libraries

Basic to any application of data processing mechanisms to existing operations is an analysis of the latter in terms which make possible a transition to a new base. A grant has been made toward the preparation of a manual of systems analysis and design as related to library operations, by Mr. Edward A. Chapman, Director of the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute Libraries and his colleague, Mr. Paul L. St. Pierre, Assistant Director for Library Operations. Arrangements for publication have been tentatively effected.

MLA International Bibliography

The Modern Language Association of America not only publishes its well known annual *International Bibliography* of scholarly work in modern languages and literatures but is also involved in the publication of other important bibliographies in the fields of literature, language, teaching and linguistics. The size and cost of these bibliographies, as well as the time consumed in printing them, point to the desirability of mechanizing their production as fully as possible. But to make such mechanization profitable, agreements must be reached with other similar publications, standards must be established, and understandings effected with users and user groups. To facilitate this effort, the Council made a grant to enable two of the Association's investigators to visit appropriate centers of similar work in Europe in the summer of 1967 in the interest of perfecting a bibliographical style which may be adopted by, or be made machine-compatible with, other major bibliographies

published here and abroad. The Council also made a parallel grant to the Association toward the costs of an International Conference on Bibliographical Form and Style, proposed to be held in the fall of 1967 at the Pennsylvania State University, at which standardization of procedures would be sought.

Indexing the Folk Song Archive Since its establishment in 1928 the Archive of Folk Song in the Music Division of the Library of Congress has grown to include some 75,000 songs and stories on 17,500 recordings. The sheer size and nature of the collection, the leading one of its kind in this country, makes cataloging by conventional methods a task of such magnitude that only the minimum of information about the content of the recordings is given in the Archive's card catalog or in various listings. The Council has made a small grant to the Library to defray the costs of a study to determine the feasibility of creating a master catalog through the use of computer technology. Such a catalog, in which each item might be indexed in depth, would not only increase the research value of the collection but through automatic manipulation would facilitate the production of a variety of printed lists, bibliographies and other reference tools.

America: History and Life Under this title the American Bibliographical Center of Santa Barbara, California, issues a quarterly journal of abstracts of publications relating to American history. The Director of the Center, Dr. Eric H. Boehm, has for years pursued a search for bibliographic devices and for technical methods by which to improve the information effectiveness of the journal. As a result the annual index of the journal makes use of a "cue" device in which the subject entries are composed of "cues"—abbreviations or acronyms—which are intended to indicate compactly and rapidly the subject, place, and years covered in each article. The Council has made a grant to the Center to write a computer program to assist in mechanizing the preparation of this index.

Other projects related to library automation The Library Technology Program of the American Library Association in collaboration with the Documentation Division of the Special Libraries Association, and with funds provided by the Council, commissioned an inventory of data processing equipment available in American libraries. This has been published.¹²

This account of projects relating to library automation, to be complete, should also include mention of the project for which a grant was made to the National Archives and Records Service. The Project, described on pages 11-12, seeks to utilize the computer in the preparation of finding aids to archival materials.

¹² *The Use of Data Processing Equipment by Libraries and Information Centers: A Survey Prepared for the Documentation Division, Special Libraries Association and Library Technology Program, American Library Association. . . .* [Chicago,] Library Technology Program, [1967]. 167 p., 23 x 33 cm

III. BIBLIOGRAPHIES

New Serial Titles The five volumes of the third edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada* came from the press, with a 1965 imprint, early in 1966.¹³ The work achieved the objective sought, namely to consolidate the scattered record of the serial holdings of North American libraries. However, it was a condition of the Council's grant with which the *List* was compiled that arrangements should be made for carrying forward, in a current and if possible self-supporting form, the record of this important category of publications in which it has been estimated that some 8,000 new titles appear each year. For this purpose there was at hand the Library of Congress publication *New Serial Titles*, which had been appearing since 1951 in monthly issues with annual and quinquennial cumulations. The Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials felt, however, that it should not rest its hopes for continuance of the record upon this publication without a test of adequacy for the purpose. In consequence it sought and received from the Council funds with which to conduct an evaluative study of the publication under the direction of Dr. Frederick A. Kuhlman, Director Emeritus of the Joint University Libraries of Nashville, Tennessee. This study is expected to be completed during 1967.

Victorian periodicals While *New Serial Titles* deals with the current record, the older record has not eluded scholarly attention. The Council has made a small grant to the Indiana University Foundation, to assist Dr. Michael Wolff, Associate Professor of English and History, to explore the feasibility of compiling an alphabetical and chronological listing, together with a subject and descriptive index, of the more than 12,000 separate newspapers and periodicals which were published in England between 1824 and 1900.

Festschriften in the field of librarianship Dr. J. Periam Danton, Professor of Librarianship at the University of California, Berkeley, has identified some 6,000 contributions in 17 languages in more than 200 Festschriften in the field of librarianship. The Council has made a small grant to the University to assist him in the completion of an index to this largely obscure but often important category of publications.

Library work for children The Council's assistance to Miss Ann Pellowski, who has had long experience with children's literature and librarianship, in completing a world bibliography of sources of information on literature and libraries for children was noted in the preceding report.¹⁴ The project has been completed and publication is expected late in 1967.

¹³ X: 35-37.

¹⁴ X: 45.

IV. BOOK SELECTION AND PROCUREMENT

Books for College Libraries. Plans for publication of a new basic list of books for academic libraries, based on the list prepared for three new undergraduate libraries in a New Campuses Program at the University of California, have been related in previous annual reports.¹⁵ In April 1967 *Books for College Libraries*, a 1,072-page listing of more than 53,000 titles, was published by the American Library Association.¹⁶ It replaces the pioneering *List of Books for College Libraries* prepared by the late Charles B. Shaw and published by the American Library Association in 1931, as well as the useful *Lamont Library Catalogue* prepared by Philip J. McNiff and published by the Harvard University Press in 1953.

The California list was prepared under the direction of Mr. Melvin J. Voigt, University Librarian of the University of California at San Diego. Development and preparation of the list was effected by Mr. Joseph H. Treyz, formerly of the New Campuses Program, now Assistant Librarian at the University of Michigan. The selections were reviewed by subject specialists chosen for competence in evaluating undergraduate college library materials. Though the list is oriented toward four-year college libraries, it has obvious uses at the university and at the community college and even high school levels.

Choice *Books for College Libraries*, 2500 copies of which were sold within the first three months of publication, includes no titles published after 1963. The vehicle for keeping the list up to date is *Choice*, a book review published 11 times a year by the American Library Association and sponsored by its member Association of College and Research Libraries. *Choice* began publication with assistance from the Council in March 1964.¹⁷ It was hoped that it might review from 2,000 to 3,000 books a year. Its Volume III, however, carried more than 5,400 reviews by more than 2,000 subject specialists. In 1967 it has more than 4,000 subscribers, including high schools as well as colleges, universities and public libraries. Despite both a subscription list and advertising revenues greater than projected, the journal is not yet completely self-supporting, principally due to the much larger number of reviews than anticipated. In consequence, the Council has, in a supplemental grant, extended its initial assistance for three years.

Book-purchasing procedures Library book-purchasing differs from most kinds of institutional procurement in at least three

¹⁵ IX: 9-10; X: 44.

¹⁶ *Books for College Libraries: A Selected List of Approximately 53,400 Titles Based on the Initial Selection Made for the University of California's New Campuses Program and Selected with the Assistance of College Teachers, Librarians, and Other Advisors.* Prepared under the direction of Melvin J. Voigt and Joseph H. Treyz. Chicago, American Library Association Publishing Department, 1967. [x], 1056 p.

¹⁷ VI: 16; VIII: 9, 19-20.

important particulars. In the case of books the purchaser seeks a particular product, i.e. a book by a specified author, with a specified title and issued by a specified publisher, rather just any good book; the purchaser usually requires this product in small quantities, most frequently perhaps in a quantity of only one, and usually seeks immediate delivery, without regard to the exhaustion of the stock already on hand.

Libraries suffer severely because of these differences. Because they are ordinarily subordinate units within larger organizations, they are frequently compelled to conduct their book-purchasing through the general procurement offices serving the entire organization. But attempts to treat books like housekeeping or hospital supplies are usually crippling to the library's efficiency.

This situation has endured for many years. From it has recently sprung another situation, equally damaging but more notorious. Under the competitive bidding procedure generally employed by procurement offices, book-procurement contracts have often been won by dealers quite incompetent to give adequate services because of lack of stock, physical facilities, staff, capital, bibliographic or bibliopolic experience, but who, while taking the profits from the easy-to-supply trade books, can plead "out of stock" or "out of print" for any book presenting difficulties in procurement.

Meanwhile, problems also exist from the point of view of the established, competent and reputable bookseller—inordinate delays between delivery and payments, complicated invoicing procedures that place a high administrative cost on him as well as on the purchaser, and the latter's refusal to accept partial deliveries on an invoice—a practice which unnecessarily delays receipt of readily available items.

To assist in the solution of these problems, the Council has made a grant to the American Library Association to enable it to sponsor jointly with the National League of Cities (representing the interest of municipal governments in the problem) a study designed to result in a manual or guide which will lead to improvement in the library-bookseller relationship. The project is under the direction of Miss Evelyn Hensel, Deputy Assistant Director for Systems and Processes, retired, of the Pennsylvania State University Libraries, who has had long experience in the field of acquisitions. She is assisted in the project by Mr. Peter Vielllette, a member of the National League of Cities staff. An advisory committee has been named under the chairmanship of Mr. W. Carl Jackson, Director of the Pennsylvania State University Libraries and formerly chairman of the ALA's Bookdealer-Library Relations Committee.

Public Law 480 Nearly ten years ago the Council made a grant to the American Council of Learned Societies for a study of the arrangements for the procurement of foreign publications

under the provisions of the Agricultural Trade Development Assistance Act of 1954 as amended.¹⁸ The (John D.) Dingell Amendment to Public Law 83-480, 1958, had provided for the use of local currencies, derived from the sale of agricultural surpluses abroad, for the purchase of books, periodicals and other materials and the deposit of these materials in libraries and research centers in the United States.

This Amendment had owed its existence in part to a suggestion by Dr. Mortimer Graves, at that time acting director of the ACLS, but for several years implementation had lagged. His report to the ACLS, made possible by the Council's grant, contributed to the development of a climate of opinion which permitted the authorization of an initial program in 1961. This program, the execution of which was entrusted to the Library of Congress, has now progressed to the point at which forty to fifty libraries have received and are making available to their scholarly communities several millions of volumes, representing thousands of titles in more than 20 foreign languages, while 310 other American libraries have been receiving a carefully chosen list of books, periodicals, and newspapers originating in nine currently participating East European and Asian countries, and involving the entire spectrum of human inquiry from archaeology to zoology.

During the past year the Council again made a grant to the American Council of Learned Societies in connection with Public Law 480—this time to enable Dr. Graves to make a tenth-year review of the acquisitions programs under the Dingell Amendment, to determine its effectiveness and the possibilities for improvement.

V. CATALOGING AND INDEXING

Shared cataloging Increasingly over the past two decades the Association of Research Libraries has recognized the importance of improving the sources of centralized cataloging available to its members. In 1957 it had learned from the Dawson study¹⁹ that the typical large academic library could expect to be able to catalog less than half its books with Library of Congress printed cards; but the next steps to be taken were not obvious. By 1964 the Association found that its members were spending about 16 per cent of their operating budgets, amounting to approximately \$18 million annually, on cataloging, but that in spite of this their cataloging arrears had increased 160 per cent

¹⁸ IV: 16; V: 31.

¹⁹ John Minto Dawson, "The acquisitions and cataloging policy of research libraries: a study of the possibilities for centralized processing." *The Library Quarterly* 27: 1-22, January 1957.

in 10 years. The need for action was urgent. Under the chairmanship of Dr. William S. Dix, the Librarian of Princeton University (and since June 1966 a member of the Board of Directors of the Council on Library Resources), the Association's committee on shared cataloging planned a multi-element program of attack on the problem. One element was an updating of the Dawson study. In 1964 and 1965 the Council made grants to the Association to effect this.²⁰ The study was conducted by Dr. James E. Skipper, Executive Secretary of the Association, with the participation of the libraries of the following universities: California/Berkeley, Chicago, Columbia, Cornell, Illinois, Michigan, Pennsylvania, Princeton, and Stanford. A report has been issued.²¹ Among the conclusions were that increased availability of cataloging copy must result from centralized, rather than cooperative, efforts and that the Library of Congress appeared to be the most logical agency to implement such a program, by extending and improving the cataloging service which it had furnished since 1901. The report also concluded that a significant improvement in the utilization of catalog information could be obtained by improving methods of distribution and identification of copy, and this, though admittedly not the whole answer, might together with automation of the bibliographic record result in increased efficiency of file maintenance and improvement of the "entry-matching" problem.

However, before this report could be studied—or even submitted—events had taken an unexpected and remarkable turn which resulted in the establishment of the National Program for Cataloging and Acquisition entrusted to the Library of Congress under Title II c of the Higher Education Act of 1965.²² Perhaps Heaven is helping those . . .

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules A long labored-for event, the publication of the new code of cataloging rules designed for the use of the English-speaking world, occurred last year. The *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*, claiming the collaboration of the American Library Association, the Library of Congress, the Library Association (of Great Britain) and the Canadian Library Association, came from the press with the first days of 1967.²³ It represents the culmination of a 30-year effort. It is "the most complete compilation of

²⁰ VIII: 15-16; IX: 18.

²¹ James E. Skipper: "The Characteristics of Cataloging in Research Libraries." The Association of Research Libraries, *Minutes of the Sixty-Eighth Meeting, July 9, 1966, New York City*. p. 55-66 (Appendix I).

²² William S. Dix, "Centralized cataloging and university libraries—Title II, Part C of the Higher Education Act of 1965." *Library Trends* 16: 97-111, July 1967.

²³ American Library Association: *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules Prepared by the American Library Association, the Library of Congress, the Library Association and the Canadian Library Association*. North American Text. Chicago: American Library Association, 1967. 400 p., 26 cm.

cataloging rules that has ever been available to American librarians."

The Council's connection with the *Rules* goes back to the first year of its own existence; its first grant was related to them. Early in 1967 the Council was approached by the American Library Association for assistance in enabling it to be represented at a meeting of German librarians at which cataloging rules were to be discussed.²⁴ At this meeting it was discovered that, contrary to current conceptions, genuine possibilities existed for harmonizing the cataloging practices of the adherents to the two principal opposing codes — the Anglo-American Rules and the Prussian Instructions.

The discovery justified reflection. In a meeting assisted by the Council it was agreed that the desirability of obtaining greater international coordination with respect to cataloging was so great as to justify the ALA in deferring some of the decisions with respect to its catalog code revision pending exploration of the possibilities. It was also agreed to look for leadership in the matter to the International Federation of Library Associations, whose Working Group on the Coordination of Cataloging Principles had been making some useful studies. Chairman of the Group was Mr. Frank C. Francis, Keeper of the Department of Printed Books of the British Museum (and since then Sir Frank Francis, K.C.B., Director and Principal Librarian of the Museum).

In consequence IFLA was encouraged to go forward in 1959 with a preliminary and in 1961 with a full scale International Conference on Cataloging Principles.²⁵ Meanwhile, in order to familiarize the international organizing committee of the Conference with the issues as seen by the American library world, the Council made travel grants to enable the members of the Committee to attend meetings on catalog code revision at Stanford University in 1958 and in Montreal in 1960.²⁶

The International Conference over, the ALA could resume the drive to completion of its code revision work, borrowing for the purpose as its editor, Mr. Sumner Spalding, on leave from his position as chief of the Descriptive Cataloging Division of the Library of Congress. As the work repeatedly exceeded its estimated term, the Council as repeatedly funded the extension until its completion. It made no secret of its desire that this should not be an exclusively American code but should, like its predecessor of 1908, involve the participation of other principal English-speaking groups.²⁷ This is gratifyingly reflected in the title of the work.

²⁴ I: 26-28; II: 10.

²⁵ IV: 13, 23; VI: 12-13.

²⁶ II: 11; IV: 13.

²⁷ V: 16; VII: 16; VIII: 14-15; IX: 16; X: 38, 76-9.

Cataloging rules for publications in Urdu, Pushto and Panjabi There is as yet no established code of cataloging rules in Pakistan or elsewhere for materials in Pushto, the official language of Afghanistan, Urdu, a commonly used language in India, or Panjabi, which with the previous two is a common literary language in West Pakistan; even the order in which a Moslem author's name should be listed may present problems. The resultant lack of uniformity in cataloging practices, sometimes even within the same institution, can be confusing and misleading. In consequence, in August 1965,²⁸ a small grant was made to Columbia University to enable Mr. Abdus Subbuh Qasimi, a teaching assistant there, to develop a cataloging code under the direction of Maurice F. Tauber, Melvil Dewey Professor of Library Science.

The project has been completed. A Code for Cataloging Materials Published in Urdu, Pushto, and Panjabi has been accepted by the committee on the doctorate of the School of Library Service and Dr. Qasimi has taken his manuscript back to the University of Peshawar in West Pakistan, where he is the principal librarian, for further refinement before publication.

Conversion of DC to LC Over the past five decades many (especially academic) libraries have replaced existing classification schemes with the Library of Congress system. This trend has markedly accelerated in the past several years. Because the scheme usually abandoned in such replacements is the (Dewey) Decimal Classification, a need has been expressed for a manual to provide guidance to those who wish to convert from DC to LC. The Council has made a grant for the preparation of such a manual to Mr. Desmond Taylor, Director of the library of the University of Puget Sound, and Mr. Raimund Matthis, Technical Services Librarian there, based upon the experience of their own library. Conversion techniques and system designs will be given emphasis, together with costs.

Book catalog vs. card catalog A grant was made to the Baltimore County Public Library, Towson, Maryland, this past year for a comparative study of cost and service aspects of its present catalog in book form as contrasted with the card catalog which it displaced.

The study has been completed and a report issued.²⁹ Among the conclusions reached are: (1) adoption of the book catalog has proved an added expense in comparison with the card catalogs, but this is not expected to continue; (2) the availability of the union catalog in each branch has resulted in greater use of the collection as a whole; intra-library loan requests rose 51 per cent over normally expected growth in 1965-66; and (3) the presence

²⁸ X: 45.

²⁹ Baltimore County Public Library: *Book Catalog and Card Catalog: A Cost and Service Study*. Towson, Maryland: The Library, 1967. 45 p. and appendixes. 28 cm.

of the book catalog in each of Baltimore County's 135 public schools, as well as in many other locations, will be a continuing asset to which no money value can be assigned.

Project Lawsearch Project Lawsearch, an attempt to apply "coordinate indexing" to the indexing of legal literature, and simultaneously requiring the development of a simple, inexpensive mechanical device for publishing and using the index, has been the subject of previous reports.³⁰ During the year the final report of the special advisory committee appointed to oversee the project by the American Association of Law Libraries in 1961 was published. The Committee, which consisted of four law librarians, Julius J. Marke, (New York University, chairman), J. Myron Jacobstein (Stanford University), Vincent E. Fiordalisi (Rutgers University), and Miles O. Price (Columbia University, emeritus) concluded that the test "with all its caveats and uncertainties, demonstrated that the coordinate search technique is a viable legal information system. In view of the potential importance of coordinate search of the law, and to further test the new implications of the statistical analysis in the area of learning and search the Committee recommends that the coordinate search system be systematically investigated on a more extensive scale".³¹

VI. LIBRARY ADMINISTRATION

The manpower shortage problem The outstanding problem in library management continues to be—as it has for several years past—in the scarcity of qualified staff, generally referred to as "the manpower shortage problem." In 1965 *The National Inventory of Library Needs*³² estimated that the national shortage in professionally trained staff meeting American Library Association standards approximates 100,000 persons. The problem is not a simple one of mere

³⁰ For reference see X: 85-6.

³¹ "Project Lawsearch. AALL Special Committee on Project Lawsearch . . . [Final Report]." *Law Library Journal* 60: 42-63, February 1967.

The following is a corrected listing of the Project Lawsearch reports:

Project Lawsearch: *Index to the Law of Motor Carriers*. [Washington, D.C.]: Project Lawsearch, The Michie Company, Matthew Bender and Company, Inc., The Bureau of National Affairs, Inc., 1962. 7 vols., 28 cm. Title varies. Contents:

[Vols. 1-3] *Index to the Law of Motor Carriers. Liability for personal injury to passengers. Liability for loss of or injury to goods. Part one [two, three]*. May 1962. 3 vols.

[Vol. 4] *Index to the Law of Motor Carriers. The Federal Motor Carriers Act*. June 1962.

[Vols. 5-6] *Index Data to the Law of Motor Carriers*. June 1962. 2 vols.

[Vol. 7] *Addendum to the Index to the Law of Motor Carriers*. September 1962.

³² Chicago: American Library Association, 1965.

recruitment and more or less uniform education; it involves such questions as whether the capabilities of present personnel are being used to the best advantage, and just what training should be given, in view of the great range of skills, many of a very specialized kind, involved in library operations.

During 1966-67 the Council made a grant to the National Book Committee, to assist an attack on the manpower problem. A portion of the grant was applied toward the expenses of a three-day Conference on Library Manpower held in Washington in March 1967, co-sponsored by the American Library Association's Office for Library Education and Library Administration Division. A number of recommendations resulted, some of which have since been implemented.³³

Another grant was made to assist the special presidential program on the manpower problem at the annual conference of the American Library Association, held in San Francisco late in June 1967.³⁴ The then president of the Association, Miss Mary Gaver, presided.

Pilferage The problem of book losses in academic libraries through theft is one which, like the weather, has been the subject of much discussion and little action. Library literature emphasizes concern with the problem but discloses little factual material on its extent or on the effectiveness of measures to control it. This past year the Council made a grant to the University of Chicago Graduate Library School to assist a study of the problem. Mrs. Maxine H. Reneker, a librarian and a student in the Graduate Library School, is to prepare descriptive and explanatory analyses of the data afforded by more than a thousand questionnaires on the pilferage problem returned by academic libraries serving student bodies of less than 5,000 persons. It is expected that the study will not only provide information on the extent of the problem—it is known to be serious—but suggest the motivations involved and methods of coping with it.

Cases in library administration A grant has been made to Dr. Mildred Hawthorth Lowell, Associate Professor of Library Science at Indiana University, to enable her to make a compilation of legal and other cases in library management. Her work is expected to result in a book with chapters on the case method of instruction, case analysis,

³³ *Library Manpower: Needs and Utilization. A conference co-sponsored by the Office for Library Education and the Library Administration Division of the American Library Association with the cooperation of the National Book Committee, March 9-11, 1967, Washington, D. C.* Edited by Lester Asheim. Chicago: American Library Association, 1967. 39 p., 25 cm.

Kathleen Molz, "Report on manpower conference." *Wilson Library Bulletin* 41: 820-23, 855 [April 1967].

"Manpower: a dialogue." *Library Journal* 92: 1799-1801, May 1, 1967.

³⁴ "Crisis in Library Manpower: Myth and Reality." *ALA Bulletin* 61: 527, May, 1967.

and actual cases, including some complicated situations involving all of the management processes.

Instruction in library use Tours, lectures, handbooks, motion pictures and other techniques are used to introduce students to the use of their libraries, but at Mt. San Antonio College, as elsewhere, students frequently return to ask staff members to repeat previously-given information. Is there another way to meet this situation? The Walnut, California, community college concluded that perhaps there is, and in 1964 was given a grant by the Council to develop an illustrated program for use with a then-new teaching-machine for the purpose of giving general information on use of the library.³⁵ Units with relevant programs were placed in five key locations in the library and a year-long study was made of their effectiveness. Results of the investigation indicate that the machines were effective in teaching the use of the library and reduced demand upon the library staff. Only 30 per cent of those using the machines required further assistance, while 57 per cent of those who had no machine instruction required assistance. The machines, however, were found to have mechanical limitations, which require correction. A report has been published.³⁶

The survey of public library systems The Council's grant to the American Library Association for a study of public library systems, noted in the preceding annual report,³⁷ was supplemented during the year just past. The ALA's member Public Library Association has contracted with Nelson Associates, New York City, to conduct the study, which involves the compilation of a list of multi-jurisdictional systems within the United States, and analysis of questionnaires returned by a statistically reliable sample of these systems with regard to their legal and administrative structure, financing, and services. Information is also being gathered to enable comparisons of present costs and services with those prior to the establishment of a system. The concluding phase of the study will be a series of six case studies illustrating major problems of system development and administration. The report resulting from the study is expected to be published in 1968.

VII. PHOTOGRAPHIC APPLICATIONS

The Hawken Manual The library world for some time stood in great need of a work that would bring up to date Herman H. Fussler's *Photographic Reproduction for Libraries* (1942) as well as Robert Binkley's *Manual on Methods*

³⁵ VIII: 36-7.

³⁶ Harriet Genung, "Can machines teach the use of the library?" *College & Research Libraries* 28: 25-30, January 1967.

³⁷ X: 59-60.

of *Reproducing Research Materials* (1931, 1936) and the International Federation for Documentation (FID)'s *Manual on Document Reproduction and Selection* (1953-8). The Council arranged for a meeting of experts to discuss the content of such a replacement and in early 1964 made a grant to the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association to commission Mr. William R. Hawken to write the book.³⁸

The work, *Copying Methods Manual*, completed under the guidance of an advisory committee during the preceding year, was published during the year just past.³⁹ It provides a comprehensive guide to the applicable processes, methods, techniques and equipment. The Library Technology Program plans to keep it up to date through the issuance of supplements.

A bibliographer's camera The Council has contracted with the R. A. Morgan Company, Palo Alto, California, for the construction and testing of a prototype of a bibliographer's camera intended to copy at from 1:1 to 1:2 magnification. The camera would be used to copy catalog or other bibliographic entries from books on a paper master to be reproduced on 5 x 3-inch paper or card copies in a scaled-down office-copying processor. Plans call for the camera to be tested at the Stanford University Library.

A portable projector for microfiches/microfilm The Council's previous annual reports have recounted its continued but unsuccessful attempts to develop a hand-held portable inexpensive device for viewing microforms.⁴⁰ Having abandoned the hope for the time for progress toward this objective, the Council has nevertheless continued to seek a device which, if not so compact as to merit the tag "hand-held," might yet mark an advance in this particular. During this past year it commissioned from the Taylor-Merchant Corporation of New York the prototype of a device for viewing microfiches, filmstrips and microfilm based upon a miniature portable slide-projector which the Corporation was already marketing.

The proposed device suggests good possibilities for use by scholars at desks or tables, in library carrels, etc. Its size should permit it to be stowed in a desk drawer when not in use, and its portability and economy should prove attractive to graduate students and others. The prototype is expected to become available during the present year.

³⁸ VIII: 35; X: 55.

³⁹ William R. Hawken: *Copying Methods Manual*. Chicago, Library Technology Program, American Library Association, 1966. 375 p.

⁴⁰ "Searching for an inexpensive hand reader for microtext," IV: 31-37 (also published as 'In quest of an optical "Grail",' *ALA Bulletin* 55: 164-7, February 1961); and other references under "Microcopy," X: 103-6.

VIII. PHYSICAL ACCESS TO LIBRARY MATERIALS

Telefacsimile in the service of library users Ever since October 21, 1948, when the entire text of *Gone With the Wind* was transmitted and reproduced in 2 minutes, 21 seconds from a local broadcasting station to the Library of Congress, where it was received in the presence of an audience assembled in the Library's Coolidge Auditorium, attempts have multiplied to put telefacsimile to work in the service of libraries and their users. The Council has assisted some of these attempts in order to test from time to time the advancing state of the art.⁴¹

The preceding annual report recounted the results of an experiment in the use of telefacsimile involving the Reno and Las Vegas campuses of the University of Nevada as well as the University of California's Davis campus — an experiment of which the limited success matched the physical limitations of the equipment.⁴² A final report of the experiment has since been issued.⁴³ At the same time a new grant was made to the Institute of Library Research of the University of California for an experiment in which copy was transmitted from the University's Berkeley to its Davis campus making use of Long Distance Xerography equipment. In this experiment typical Xerox copies were transmitted on a signal of television frequency from Berkeley to the Vacaville Hills, whence it was retransmitted to Davis, altogether a distance of about 75 miles.

The project was designed both to test the equipment and to develop procedures for quicker intercampus interlibrary loan service. Borrowers were advised that they might telephone requests for interlibrary loans of journal articles directly to local offices; these were answered with LDX copies. To test quality and resolution, a variety of materials were selected for transmission. The experiment has been concluded and a report is in preparation; procedures and costs are to be discussed.

Another experiment in the transmission of library material is discussed in the report on the Council's assistance to Project Intrex, described earlier.

Home delivery of books Among the deterrents to the use of libraries are the time required to visit them, difficulties of transportation including parking, lack of ability to use the bibliographical apparatus, and frustration from failure to find material. It has been urged from time to time that these

⁴¹ "Telecommunication," X: 116-7.

⁴² X:49.

⁴³ H. G. Morehouse: *Telefacsimile Services Between Libraries With the Xerox Magnavox Telecopier . . . A study prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. . . .* Reno: University of Nevada Library, 1966. 54 p., 28 cm.

obstacles could be reduced or avoided by a system of home delivery of books in which the user would specify his needs by mail or telephone, the reference work would be performed by the library's staff and the material would be transmitted by mail or delivery truck. Such services exist in a few subscription libraries, and some public library systems maintain them for the benefit of shut-ins, but there has been no recent demonstration of a general home delivery service. In 1961 the Council made a grant for the demonstration of such a service to the Citizens' Library of Washington, Pennsylvania, but the results were obscured by irrelevant factors and no final report has been published.⁴⁴

The idea has persisted, however, and has recently awakened renewed interest. In order to encourage discussion the Council co-sponsored, with the San Antonio (Texas) Public Library, a meeting on the subject during the American Library Association's annual conference in San Francisco in June 1967, at which 52 persons were present for four sessions spread over two days.⁴⁵ It was the consensus of the meeting that the idea should be demonstrated with adequate support under the observation of a widely representative advisory body.

IX. PLANNING

The long-term needs of research libraries Early in 1961 discussions were held at the White House looking to the possible naming of a Presidential commission on libraries.⁴⁶ These discussions had no immediate results, and supposing the plan to have been abandoned by the other participants, the American Council of Learned Societies recently requested, and the Council authorized, a grant to establish a commission which would concern itself principally with the future needs of research libraries and with the arrangements required to meet the needs.

However, before the grant was made, President Johnson on September 2, 1966 named a 15-member National Advisory Commission on Libraries, to report in one year a national plan for library development.⁴⁷ Faced with such a task, the Commission has requested the ACLS to provide a report on the needs of research libraries and the Council's grant has been made available

⁴⁴ VI: 32. Cf. R. T. Jordan, "Home delivery of books." *Wilson Library Bulletin*, December 1967 (in press).

⁴⁵ *Conference on Books by Mail, Sheraton-Palace Hotel, San Francisco, California, June 24-25, 1967. Report of Proceedings.* Washington, D. C.: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1967. 22 p., 27 cm.

⁴⁶ "White House Conference." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 22: 35-6, January 28, 1963.

⁴⁷ U. S. President, Executive Order 11301.

to fund the study upon which this report will be based. ACLS has assembled for the purpose a distinguished advisory and working group for which Dr. Thomas P. Brockway, formerly professor of history and dean of Bennington College, is serving as staff director.

The Federal Library Committee The establishment and work of the Federal Library Committee have been referred to in previous annual reports.⁴⁸ The Committee, whose purpose is to improve coordination and planning among the Federal libraries, is composed of 12 permanent members, representing the Library of Congress, National Agricultural Library, National Library of Medicine, and the libraries of nine Executive departments — Commerce, Defense, Interior, Justice, Labor, Post Office, State, Treasury, and Health, Education, and Welfare. Six other members represent independent Federal agencies on a rotating basis.

The Committee maintains a small secretariat whose offices are in the Library of Congress. One of the objectives has been to improve communication among the Federal libraries, and in a number of matters relationships have been established where previously none existed. A *Newsletter*, instituted on a continuing basis, reaches more than five hundred Federal libraries about the world, and an orientation program for Federal librarians has been well attended. Various recruiting measures have been undertaken, a statistical survey of special libraries serving the Federal Government has been prepared, as has a compilation of the laws and regulations affecting Federal libraries. Various task forces have been put to work, e.g., on automation, acquisition of materials, and correlation of Federal library resources. The Committee issues an annual report.

Resources of Canadian university libraries Late in 1961 the Council made a small grant to the National Conference of Canadian Colleges and Universities to enable it to commission a survey of research library resources in the humanities and social sciences. The survey, conducted by Mr. Edwin E. Williams, Counsellor on Collections in the Harvard University Library, was successful not only in stimulating increased support of acquisitions but in inspiring surveys of collections in other disciplines.⁴⁹ This in turn led the Association of Universities and Colleges of Canada (successor to the National Conference) and the Canadian Association of College and University Libraries to develop a plan for a Canada-wide survey of library resources at various levels of study (undergraduate, masters', doctoral, etc.) and of institutional practice (small colleges, medium and large-size universities, etc.). Questions

⁴⁸ III: 40-1; VIII: 44-5; IX: 45-6; X: 58-9.

⁴⁹ VI: 39; VII: 19-20.

of service, administration and financial support are other aspects of the investigation.

The Council has made a grant to support the study. The resulting report is expected to provide guidance to university administrators, library directors, and faculties in planning the development of library resources and the expansion of regional and nation-wide library services in the libraries of Canadian colleges and universities for some years to come.

**International
Relations
Office of the
American Library
Association**

In 1961 the Council made a five-year grant to the American Library Association to provide for an assistant director and related expenses for its International Relations Office, which was already receiving principal support from other sources, but which needed this additional assistance in order to be able to provide continuing service.⁵⁰ The term of the grant has now expired, and a final report shows that the office has accomplished much useful work during the period. Much of this is in the nature of planning which may be expected to bear fruit in the future, but in addition the Office has been enabled to accept responsibility for administration of library programs in Brazil, Ethiopia, India, the Philippines and elsewhere, as well as planning the itineraries of foreign librarians visiting the United States and assisting in placing American librarians abroad.

**Arizona
library
survey**

Library services in Arizona have been recognized by its librarians and educators to be among the least-developed in the country; but steps have recently been taken to improve the situation. The State Department of Library and Archives commissioned from the Bureau of Educational Research and Services of the College of Education of the Arizona State University a comprehensive, state-wide library survey. Upon its completion it was determined to exploit its findings as rapidly as possible by holding a seminar to discuss its report. The Council made a grant to the University for this purpose. The seminar, held in Chandler in May 1967, was attended by members of the Arizona Library Advisory Committee, state legislative leaders and state officials, civic leaders and others — 33 in all. Plans, including priorities and draft legislation for implementing the survey recommendations, were developed.

**Education
for
librarianship**

The Graduate School of Library Science of the University of Illinois opened the observance of its 75th anniversary with an international conference on education for librarianship, held in Urbana in June 1967. Fifteen countries were represented at the five-day conference, the principal purpose of which was to assess the current trends of library training in the United States and abroad,

⁵⁰ VI: 40.

especially in Europe and Latin America, and to draw guidelines for the future. Subjects discussed included: history and present status of education for librarianship, organization and operation of library schools, curriculum principles and practices, teaching methods, and advanced study and research. The proceedings of the conference are to be published. The Council assisted the conference with a grant toward the travel expenses of foreign speakers and the translation of their papers into English.

Council of National Library Associations As a result of the Council's grant, recorded in the preceding report,⁵¹ a planning group of the Council of National Library Associations held a number of meetings and has prepared a plan of action for the future. It involves increasing the representation of the Council to include information services. This proposal has been adopted in principle by several of the constituent associations and is now awaiting discussion.

X. PRESERVATION OF LIBRARY MATERIALS

A national plan for the preservation of deteriorating research library materials Following publication of the results of the investigations of W. J. Barrow indicating that few of the books published in the first half of the 20th century will be usable in the next century, the Association of Research Libraries established a Committee on the Preservation of Research Library Materials. The first question put by the Committee was: What is the size of the preservation task? To find an answer to this question the Council made a grant to enable the Committee to commission certain statistical studies. The results, which have been published, indicate that the materials in American libraries requiring preservation attention number (in single copy) some three billion pages.⁵²

As a next step, in 1962 the Council made a grant to assist the Association and its Committee to develop an overall plan to meet this problem. Mr. Gordon R. Williams, Director of the Midwest Inter-Library Center, Chicago (since renamed the Center for Research Libraries) was assigned to investigate. His report was rendered in the fall of 1964, was adopted by the Association at its Midwinter meeting in January 1965 and was published in January 1966.⁵³ This was substantially the situation at the opening of the year covered by the present Report.

⁵¹ X: 62.

⁵² VI: 22-3; IX: 29-31; X: 82-3.

⁵³ Gordon R. Williams, "The preservation of deteriorating material." *Library Journal* 91: 51-6, 189-94, January 1, 15, 1966.

Central to the ARL proposal is its execution by a national agency that will represent the research libraries with responsibility for assuring "the physical preservation for as long as possible of at least one copy of every deteriorating record, and that will make copies of these records available to any library when required." In practical terms, this pointed at least initially to the Library of Congress.

That institution, while interested and entirely sympathetic, was nevertheless not prepared to accept uncritical responsibility for the proposed program. It was neither wholly persuaded by the report, nor — if it were — did it have the resources in funds or staff to pursue its recommendations immediately. However, the Committee and the Library found a middle ground on which progress toward the objective might be made (with the Council's assistance) while not making any irreversible commitments with respect to preservation procedure.

The Library of Congress has for some time been segregating its badly deteriorated books in a "brittle books" collection. Under arrangements with the Association of Research Libraries, to which the Council has made a grant for the purpose, the Library is exploring the administrative and bibliographic (as contrasted with the laboratory) arrangements for assuring the preservation of these books for the continuing uses of the research community. This exploration involves providing answers to such questions as: What are the best methods for comparing the condition of copies of the same book at different locations and for selecting the copy most suitable for preservation? What record is to be made of the preserved copy, and where?

A report of this investigation is expected early in 1968. Future developments of the national plan will make use of the experience gained in it.

The The work of this laboratory, which is indebted for
W. J. Barrow its fine quarters in Richmond to the hospitality of
Research the Virginia Historical Society, has been described
Laboratory in previous reports.⁵⁴ During the past year the
Laboratory continued to conduct investigations on
behalf of the Council related to the preservation of library ma-
terials. Principal attention was given to the following:

- Book papers of the 19th century. An investigation intended to ascertain and if possible explain the present condition of those papers and to suggest methods for preservative treatment if found to be needed.
- Book papers of the 17th and 18th centuries. Continuation of the foregoing.

⁵⁴ VI: 21-2; VII: 20-3; VIII: 29-32; IX: 12, 31-2, 33-5; X: 19, 47-9.

- The effects of storage temperature on the permanence/durability of book papers.
- The effects of humidity in storage atmosphere on the permanence/durability of book papers.

In connection with the first of these investigations it became apparent that a new test—for flax fiber—was needed. Linen rags served as the principal source of fiber for paper in the western world until they were largely displaced by cotton rags in the 19th century. It was found desirable to observe the shift in order to identify any accompanying effects. A method of discriminating between flax and cotton fiber was developed and applied on a sampling basis to a number of the papers which had been tested. By the end of the year a report of the investigation of the 19th century papers was undergoing final revision before being sent to press.

The examination of the papers of the early 19th century but more especially of the prior centuries similarly called attention to the need for a separate test for alum. It is well known that papermaker's alum, in conjunction with rosin, came into wide use for engine-sizing during the 19th century, and there is a standard test (the Raspail test) for the presence of this size. However, alum was used in paper making long before the 19th century, and its effect on the permanence/durability of paper has not been studied. Accordingly, during the year the Laboratory began to apply a test for the presence of alum regardless of its association with rosin.

The Laboratory also completed several smaller studies. One of these concerned the comparative permanence/durability of competitive brands of mending tissue paper of the kind used as reinforcement in the lamination of weakened documents with cellulose acetate film. The results of this study have been published.⁵⁵ In order to conduct the study it was necessary to develop suitable testing techniques because the ordinary tests for paper (such as the folding test under tension) are not applicable to materials as delicate as are these tissues.

Mr. Barrow had taken advantage of the study of 19th century papers to test the validity of a color spot-test for quickly identifying papers in need of preservative treatment. The chlorophenol-red spot-test for acidity gave sufficiently consistent results over the entire range of the century to deserve further development, and by the end of the year a series of tests had been conducted on modern paper with the intention of publishing a brochure describing and giving the results of various spot-tests.

⁵⁵ W. J. Barrow, "Acidity: an undesirable property in paste and mending tissue." *American Archivist* 30: 190-3, January 1967.

W. J. Barrow and Ann M. Carlton, "Durability of three current laminating tissues." *Ibid.* 30: 526-9, July 1967.

The same, "Permanence of three current laminating tissues." *Ibid.*, January 1968 (in press).

In contracting for the estimated 610-volume publication of the pre-1956 imprint portion of the National Union Catalog, the American Library Association specified a permanent/durable paper of the type developed and recommended by Mr. Barrow in 1959.⁵⁶ The publication contract was awarded to a British firm which found compliance with the specification difficult due as much to the lack of access to adequate testing facilities as to the inability of paper manufacturers to comply. Accordingly, at the request of the cognizant ALA committee (the Committee on Resources of the Resources and Technical Services Division) the Council authorized Mr. Barrow to assist, and, after conducting some preliminary tests, he went to England in June 1967, where, working with the publishers, various paper mills and research groups, he was successful in developing the arrangements for producing the required paper. The Laboratory will continue to provide testing services in this connection until the arrangements seem to be stabilized and other testing facilities are found.

Shortly before the end of the year the Council renewed its contract with the Laboratory for another year.⁵⁷

Library bookbinding As the result of an inquiry conducted in 1960 under the sponsorship of the Bookbinding Committee of the American Library Association (together with a representative of the Special Libraries Association) with the Council's support, a study was designed looking to the development of performance standards for library binding.⁵⁸ The study was initiated in 1962 under the direction of the American Library Association's Library Technology Project and the guidance of an advisory committee representing both that Association and the Special Libraries Association. A contract for the all-important development of tests, and testing devices, for measuring the performance of bindings was placed by LTP with the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. In the following four years the Laboratory examined many thousands of worn bindings to ascertain the effects of age and use and constructed a testing device which very satisfactorily simulates these effects in a laboratory environment.⁵⁹ LTP purchased many hundreds of new books and placed them in hard-usage situations in libraries throughout the country, after which they were returned for examination to the Laboratory. An immediate result of the study was the publication by LTP of three provisional performance standards for library bindings — for

⁵⁶ "[Publication of pre-1956 National Union Catalog.]" *ALA Bulletin* 61: 238-9, March 1967.

⁵⁷ Mr. Barrow suffered a fatal heart-attack on August 25, 1967. See Appendix.

⁵⁸ IV: 18; V: 20, 45.

⁵⁹ F. G. Poole, "Performance standards in library binding." *Book Production Magazine* 75: 67-8, June 1962.

W. J. Barrow, "New device tests performance of library bindings." *Ibid.* 79: 60-2, March 1964.

durability, openability and workmanship.⁶⁰ LTP has also taken steps to implement these standards by arranging for the availability of the testing devices and by proposing the provisional standards as American standards to the United States of America Standards Institute.

Deacidification of entire volumes As a result of the work of W. J. Barrow, the necessity for neutralizing acidity in deteriorating paper as a prerequisite to its preservation is generally accepted throughout the world. The deacidification procedure developed by Mr. Barrow, is however, a manual process devised for separate sheets of paper and not readily applicable to bound volumes. In an effort to develop a process for the latter purpose he was not able to find a suitable procedure based upon either exposure of the book to vapor or immersion in liquid, but was compelled to accept a compromise technique making use of an aerosol spray.⁶¹ Meanwhile, the plans for a national program for the preservation of research library materials, to which reference is made above, assume the availability of an economically feasible deacidification process and emphasize the need for one less expensive than any now available.

Recently, at the Graduate Library School of the University of Chicago Mr. Richard D. Smith obtained some promising results in deacidification of entire volumes from liquid immersion.⁶² The Council has in consequence made a grant to the University to enable him to prosecute the inquiry thus suggested. He has been assured of assistance in his inquiry by the advice of the University's Chemistry Department, the Institute of Paper Chemistry at Appleton, Wisconsin, and others.

XI. RESOURCES

National Register of Microform Masters The study of the bibliographical problems connected with the microforms, which was conducted in 1965 by Professor Wesley Simonton under the sponsorship of the Association of Research Libraries with assistance from the Council, identified as an urgent requirement the creation of a national register of the master copies (negative or other) of microforms

⁶⁰ American Library Association. *Library Technology Project: Development of Performance Standards for Binding Used in Libraries, Phase II. Report on a study conducted by Library Technology Project.* Chicago, [1966]. viii, 54 p., 24 cm.

⁶¹ W. J. Barrow, *Spray Deacidification.* Richmond, Virginia. W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, 1964. (Permanence/Durability of the Book - III).

⁶² Richard Daniel Smith, "Paper deacidification: a preliminary report." *Library Quarterly* 36: 273-292, October 1966.

meeting suitable tests for adequacy, not only in the interest of calling attention to what is already available but—quite as important—reducing the risk, at that time very high, of unknowing duplication of effort.

Accordingly, in January 1965 the Council made a two-year grant to the Library of Congress to facilitate the establishment of the National Register of Microform Masters.⁶³ The Register is concerned only with master copies, which are defined as those which are held solely for the purpose of making further copies. For the purposes envisioned by the Register, single copies from the masters must be made available at any time and for a reasonable fee. The Register includes, too, a second category of masters—those which in addition to meeting the foregoing requirements are housed in temperature-controlled, fire-proof space and are owned by a responsible non-profit institution.

The first issues of the published *National Register of Microform Masters*, uniform in format with the other Library of Congress catalogs and provided free to subscribers to the *National Union Catalog*, were published in September 1965 and January 1966. A first annual cumulation, listing 21,500 titles assembled from 33 sources, was published in late 1966.⁶⁴ It is expected that a second cumulation, listing 17,500 additional titles from 50 sources, will appear before the end of 1967.

While the editorial work on the National Register is of course the specific contribution of the Library of Congress, this is a genuinely cooperative venture to which many libraries and even commercial establishments, including foreign establishments, have contributed.

It is gratifying to be able to report that the Library has informed the Council that, following the exhaustion of the grant with the assistance of which the National Register was established, the Library has been able to incorporate it into its ongoing program.

**Center for the
Coordination of
Foreign
Microform
Copying** Whereas the National Register of Microform Masters is concerned with the microcopying of printed material, the Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying is concerned with the copying of unpublished source material.

Like the former, the Center was established in 1965 with the aid of a grant from the Council for an experimental

⁶³ IX: 23-4; see also Edmond L. Applebaum, "Implications of the *National Register of Microform Masters* as part of a national preservation program," *Library Resources & Technical Services* 9: 489-94, Fall 1965; Fred Blum, "The *National Register of Microform Masters (NRMM)*," *Microcosm* 12: 1: 3, June 1967.

⁶⁴ Library of Congress, *National Register of Microform Masters*, compiled by the Library of Congress in cooperation with the American Library Association and the Association of Research Libraries. Washington: The Library of Congress, 1966-. Irregular, with annual cumulations.

period terminating in 1969, thereby similarly implementing a recommendation of earlier studies.⁶⁵ The Center endeavors to coordinate photocopying projects conducted in foreign archives and libraries by American institutions and individuals and to prevent duplication of effort and expense through cooperative planning. The Center also identifies extensive photocopying projects which are planned, underway or completed; it records the location of copies of foreign collections in this country; and it assists American institutions in learning which manuscript collections can be photographed in foreign libraries and archives and disseminates this information to the scholarly community. In carrying out its work the Center has the cooperation of American libraries, universities, learned societies and government agencies. It has published one report.⁶⁶

**The International
Inventory of
Musical Sources**

This record (known as RISM from its French title, *Répertoire International des Sources Musicales*) is a joint venture of the International Association of Music Libraries and of the International Musicological Society. It proposes to inventory in some 30 published volumes (the first of which was published in 1960) the sources for the history of music to 1800. American participation in work on RISM is in the hands of a joint committee representing the Music Library Association and the American Musicological Society. The Council has made five grants during the past decade in aid of this project.⁶⁷ The first of these made possible American participation in the original planning of the *Inventory*. Others assisted in the establishment of an editorial office at Kassel, Germany, and in the publication of the first volume. The two most recent grants enabled the American group to assemble at the Library of Congress the records of holdings of American libraries suitable for inclusion in RISM, to edit and forward these to Europe, with copies going to the National Union Catalog. With the American contribution 95 per cent complete, the office in the Library of Congress was closed toward the end of 1965 and the remaining work was assumed by the Library's Music Division. A report on American participation in the project has now been issued.⁶⁸ It records that "approximately 52,900 American items were reported during the entire span of the American office. . . . These items represent the holdings of 261 institutions . . . which hold pre-1801 musical material." It is interesting to note that among the items are a number of unica.

⁶⁵ IX: 24.

⁶⁶ *News from the Center [for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying.]* Washington, D. C.: Library of Congress, No. 1, Spring, 1967 (reprinted from *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*, February 16, 1967).

⁶⁷ III: 28; V: 19; VI: 14-5; VII: 17-8.

⁶⁸ *International Inventory of Musical Sources (Répertoire International des Sources Musicales) Report of the Joint U. S. Committee On Activities to January 1, 1966 . . .* Prepared by Wayne D. Shirley. Washington, D. C. 1966. 23 p.

Oriental studies The International Congress of Orientalists is not a continuing organization but comes into existence intermittently, each Congress being in the hands of an organizing committee representing the host country. Beginning with the first meeting in Paris in 1873, there have been 26 Congresses; all except the 1964 meeting in New Delhi have been held in Western or Central Europe. The XXVII International Congress is to be held in August 1967 at the University of Michigan with the Association for Asian Studies and the American Oriental Society as co-sponsors. Some 2,000 Orientalists from all parts of the world are expected to attend.

In addition to being the first Congress to be held in the United States, this is the first to include in its plans a conference-long panel on library resources for Oriental studies. In this connection, the Council has made a grant to the Association for Asian Studies to assist in meeting the travel expenses of a number of librarians from overseas to attend the Congress. The significance attached to the library panel lies in the facts that no single institution in any country can be self-sufficient in building up, processing and maintaining library resources adequate for Oriental studies and that there is concurrently little international coordination or collaboration in this work. It is hoped that the forthcoming meetings will improve this situation.

XII. TESTING AND STANDARDIZATION

Library Technology Program The Library Technology Project (in 1966 renamed the "Library Technology Program") came into being through the instrumentality of the Council on May 1, 1959, as an activity of the American Library Association designed to meet the need for a continuing program of testing and standardization of library supplies, equipment, and systems.⁶⁹ The Council has been the principal support of LTP since the beginning, but, as related in the previous annual report,⁷⁰ the activity has begun to find other sources of income. During the past 14 months (two months were added to the project year to permit adjustment to ALA's fiscal year) the Council provided 58 per cent of LTP's total budget whereas in the preceding 12 months it had contributed 74 per cent. ALA's contribution grew from 5 per cent in 1965-66 to 10 per cent this past year. Revenues from *Library Technology Reports*, a bi-monthly subscription service, provided for 22 per cent of the total budget this past year, the Publications Revolving Fund 9 per cent, and 1 per cent came from such sources as royalties. This year the Council has again renewed its support of LTP.

⁶⁹ III: 38-9.

⁷⁰ X: 54.

In addition to such continuing activities as reporting on library supplies, equipment and systems regularly in the *ALA Bulletin*, *Special Libraries*, and *Library Technology Reports*, and answering inquiries on these subjects, a number of projects were completed or initiated this past year. Some of these have already been mentioned, e.g., the inventory of data processing equipment in American libraries (p. 17), the completion of the *Hawken Copying Methods Manual* (pp. 27-28) and the study of performance standards for library bookbinding (pp. 36-37). Others included:

- Renewal of work on a manual on library furniture. Drawing on an earlier, fruitless attempt,⁷¹ plans were made this past year for a manual of greater scope, and Mr. Donald E. Bean, president of Library Management and Building Consultants, Inc., who has worked widely in planning equipment for libraries, has been commissioned to prepare it. The effort is expected to require two years.
- Testing of 24 earphone-equipped record players for their suitability for library use. This will be the third such evaluation commissioned by LTP, occasioned by the changes in the record player market.⁷² The testing is to be performed by the United States Testing Company.
- A test of forty to fifty wood and plastic chairs intended for general seating in libraries with a view to identifying (a) the specific data upon which sound choices of chairs can be based, (b) reasonable performance tests for chairs, and (c) performance tests useful for establishing manufacturing specifications. If success is achieved in the last particular, a national standard will be sought through United States of America Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z85 (Library Equipment and Supplies). The project is for 29 months, and the testing is to be conducted by Buyers Laboratory of New York.
- Evaluation of carpet underlays. This study, commenced in 1964, has been completed and a report was published during the past year.⁷³

**Standards for
Machine Input of
Bibliographical
Records**

In December 1965 the Council made, jointly with the National Science Foundation, a three-year grant to the University of North Carolina for the work of Sectional Committee Z39 of the United States of America Standards Institute which has responsibility for the development of standards in the field of library work and documentation. The Committee is

⁷¹ VII: 39; IX: 44.

⁷² VIII: 35-6; IX: 43.

⁷³ IX: 42-3.

Foster D. Snell, Inc.: *Carpet Underlays: Performance Characteristics*. New York: Institutional Research Council [1967]. 31 p., 28 cms.

sponsored by the Council of National Library Associations and its chairman is currently Dr. Jerrold Orne, Librarian of the University of North Carolina.⁷⁴

During this past year, together with the National Science Foundation, the Council made a supplemental grant to enable the Committee to commence a task not originally contemplated, viz., development of a standard for "machine input of bibliographical records," by which is meant the conversion of bibliographic data such as the data on library catalog cards to machine-readable form (i.e., punched cards or computer tape). The project has been completed and a report has been published.⁷⁵ It is intended to serve as a working document for the Subcommittee that created it rather than as a finished standard.

⁷⁴ X: 58.

⁷⁵ Ann T. Curran and Henriette D. Avram: *The Identification of Data Elements in Bibliographic Records*. Final Report of the Special Project on Data Elements for the Subcommittee on Machine Input Records (SC-2) of the Sectional Committee on Library Work and Documentation (Z-39) of the United States of America Standards Institute. N. p., May 1967. 126 p., 28 cms.

APPENDIX

WILLIAM J. BARROW

DEATH OF WILLIAM J. BARROW*

Libraries and archives and all who depend on them lost one of their most effective collaborators in the sudden death from a heart attack on August 25, 1967 of William J. Barrow, documents restorer by profession and Director of the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Richmond, Virginia.

Mr. Barrow's name will continue to be associated with the cylindrical laminator which he invented for use in the restoration of documents, with the Barrow process for deacidification of paper as an essential part of the restoration process, with the demonstration of the actual facts of paper stability over the past four centuries, with the development of a permanent/durable book paper marketable within the price range of commercial book papers, and with other notable investigations connected with paper and ink, over a period of some thirty years.

Mr. Barrow was born on December 11, 1904 in Brunswick County, Virginia, the son of a physician, Dr. Bernard Barrow, and Sallie Virginia Archer Barrow. He graduated from Randolph-Macon Academy in 1923 and attended Randolph-Macon College, 1923-5. In 1932, in the course of research into family records, he became interested in document preservation. Encouraged by Dr. R. H. McIlwaine, who as State Librarian of Virginia felt the need of scientific attention to this matter, he prepared himself by taking instruction in bookbinding and by observing at the Library of Congress the methods of document restoration then in vogue which left much to be desired in meeting alarming problems of deterioration. Dr. McIlwaine gave him workshop space in the Virginia State Library where he undertook assignments in document restoration.

His reputation soon spread, and he was invited to establish a larger workshop at the Mariners' Museum in Newport News. While there he developed his cylindrical press for laminating documents with cellulose acetate foil which had earlier been found suitable for this purpose by the National Bureau of Standards. For this development he has received international recognition. In 1936, for example, he was elected a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts, London, and his laminators have been installed in principal libraries and archives around the world, including the Library of Congress, British Museum, Bibliothèque Nationale, Paris and the national archives of France and Belgium. (One of his laminators is currently on the way to India, where he was planning to supervise its installation next fall.)

* Reprinted from the Council's *Recent Developments*, no. 247, August 28, 1967

Back at the Virginia State Library in Richmond (where he operated the document repair shop until his death), Mr. Barrow continued to improve his process. An early development was intended to strengthen laminated documents. Because cellulose acetate tears very easily, he added sheets of fine strong tissue to the laminate sandwich.

The next improvement was of focal importance, not only for lamination but for all subsequent developments. Mr. Barrow began to wonder what would happen to the documents that he was laminating; he reasoned that the progressive deterioration that had made lamination necessary would continue despite lamination. This reasoning stimulated him to investigations that convinced him of the principal role played by acidity in the deterioration of paper. As a result, in the years 1940-1945 he developed his deacidification process using solutions of calcium hydroxide, calcium bicarbonate and/or magnesium bicarbonate as an essential part of the restoration process. This technique was validated by the National Bureau of Standards in 1957 after the unfortunate experiences of some repositories had shown that lamination by itself is insufficient to assure preservation.

In the ensuing years Mr. Barrow lost none of the many opportunities which came his way to study old papers and inks and to publish his findings when he could find the leisure. Among other things he discovered how to deacidify documents with water-soluble inks, and he invented a process of ink-lifting whereby the actual print (or other writing) can be lifted from the surface of deteriorated paper and transferred to new strong paper. The Library of Congress has availed itself of this technique for a number of important books.

By 1957 Mr. Barrow had developed a number of hypotheses regarding the causes and cures of paper deterioration and was anxious to test them. In that year, in an investigation sponsored by the Virginia State Library with funding from the Council on Library Resources, he was given the opportunity to ascertain by the careful testing and measurement of 500 books for the period 1900-1949 just what happened to book-paper in the 20th century. He found that the most alarmist views of deterioration were not exaggerated; that the paper in the average book of 1900-1910 retained only 4 per cent of what is supposed to have been its initial strength and may be expected to be unusable by the year 2000; that paper in books even in 1940-49 had already in 1957-58 lost 64 per cent of the initial strength; that the principal culprit for this deterioration was not, as commonly thought, polluted industrial atmosphere (although this plays a minor part) but manufacturing processes.

Accordingly, in a second investigation undertaken for the Virginia State Library in 1959, Mr. Barrow set out to discover whether a paper could avoid these processes and still be manufactured

economically. His inquiry was successful; the result was a "permanent/durable" book paper made from chemical wood pulp but having an expectation of longevity comparable to that of the fine book papers of the past, yet still within the normal price range. A number of paper manufacturers are now offering papers which to greater or lesser degree meet the Barrow specifications.

Of these two investigations the Council on Library Resources said in 1960:

The results of these two projects, even if they should go no further than they have gone to date, may be regarded as constituting a remarkable achievement. A solitary worker — in this day of group research — unconnected with the complex technology and economics of paper manufacture and use, save as his interest in the subject was stimulated by his activities in document restoration, has in the short space of three years been able to concentrate attention on the causes of paper deterioration, to identify the principal target for attack, and to succeed in providing a feasible solution — commanding the respect of the experts — to a problem which has been for three quarters of a century one of the most stultifying and baffling that libraries have faced.

Up to this point, most of Mr. Barrow's work had been achieved with the meager facilities of his repair shop in the Virginia State Library. It was obvious that he should be better equipped. In consequence, in 1961, with assistance from the Council on Library Resources, he took advantage of the hospitality of the Virginia Historical Society to construct in its building a paper testing laboratory employing the most exacting controls of temperature and humidity, and devoted exclusively to problems of preservation of library materials. There with a small staff he has carried out a series of important investigations for the Council the results of which have been reported in a series of publications entitled "Permanence/Durability of the Book." Among these have been an investigation of methods for deacidification of entire books (as contrasted with deacidification of separate pages), development of methods for predicting the longevity of adhesives suitable for "perfect" binding and the selection of suitable adhesives for this purpose; investigations of what happened to book papers from 1900 back to the 16th century; and the effect of storage temperature upon the permanence of paper. In addition, the Laboratory undertook the experimental work toward developing performance standards (and the necessary testing devices) for library book binding on behalf of the American Library Association. Another investigation has led to improvement of the stock used for library catalog cards.

At the time of his death Mr. Barrow was, in addition to the regular work of the Laboratory, seeing two publications through

the press. He had just returned from England, where, on behalf of the American Library Association, he had been consulting with British paper manufacturers in an effort to assure a permanent/durable paper for the forthcoming 610-volume publication of the National Union Catalog; and he was conducting some experiments in combined resizing and deacidification in connection with the restoration work in the flood-damaged libraries of Florence.

In addition to an intense curiosity with regard to matters of everyday experience, Mr. Barrow had a genius for experimentation and investigation. Several of the investigations in which he came to useful conclusions were said on good authority to be "impossible." Thus it was not thought possible to make useful predictions of the longevity of polyvinyl acetate adhesive in the absence of a record of natural aging. Mr. Barrow found ways for substituting for the natural experience. Similarly with the effect of storage temperature on paper longevity: changes in paper stored at room temperatures or below are ordinarily too slow to be observable within available time limits. Mr. Barrow found ways to accelerate them. His scientific training was admittedly meager, but he was careful to secure the advice of specialists in the planning and evaluation of his experiments. At bottom, however, his success derived from the accuracy of intuitions based on an instinctive feeling for materials and processes, reinforced by years of intelligent observation.

In addition to these qualities, Mr. Barrow's affability and readiness to assist won him friends on five continents. Even when compelled to refuse his refusal was a courtesy.

Mr. Barrow's career was compressed by *Publishers' Weekly*—in the title of an article which it published in April 1966 on the Barrow Laboratory—into the single phrase, "The Thirty Years That Revolutionized Paper."

Mr. Barrow's bibliography is a long one; the following are among his most important publications:

Barrow, William J.: *The Barrow method of restoring deteriorated documents*. Richmond, Virginia: W. J. Barrow, 1965. 19 p.

———: Black writing ink of the Colonial period. *The American Archivist* 11:291-307, October 1948.

———: *Manuscripts and documents: their deterioration and restoration*. Charlottesville: University of Virginia Press, 1955. 86 p.

———: *Permanence and durability of library catalog cards. A study conducted by W. J. Barrow for the Library Technology Project*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1961]. 40 p.

———: *Procedures and equipment used in the Barrow method of restoring manuscripts and documents*. Richmond, Virginia: W. J. Barrow, State Library Building, 1961. 15 p.

Barrow, William J. and Sproull, Reavis: *Permanence in book papers*. *Science* 129:1075-1084, April 24, 1959.

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory: *Permanence/durability of the book*. Richmond, Virginia, 1963 —.

- I. A two-year research project. 1963. 46 p.
- II. Test data of naturally aged papers. 1964. 79 p.
- III. Spray deacidification. 1964. 62 p.
- IV. Polyvinyl acetate (PVA) adhesives for use in library bookbinding. 1965. 66 p.
- V. Strength and other characteristics of book papers, 1800-1899. In press.

Virginia State Library: *Deterioration of book stock, causes and remedies: two studies on the permanence of paper, conducted by W. J. Barrow, edited by Randolph W. Church*. Richmond: The Virginia State Library, 1959, 72 p.

———: *The manufacture and testing of durable book papers, based on the investigations of W. J. Barrow, edited by Randolph W. Church*. Richmond: The Virginia State Library, 1960. 64 p.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

September 8, 1967

To the Board of Directors of

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1967 and its expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1967

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 232,057
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximates market)	\$ 297,227	
Savings account	514,974	
Certificates of deposit, at cost plus accrued interest	<u>611,077</u>	1,423,278
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in quarterly instalments of \$250,000 (Note)		1,750,000
Deposits		<u>580</u>
		<u><u>\$3,405,915</u></u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see Exhibit III)		\$ 977,571
Accounts payable, accrued salaries and withheld taxes		7,786
Fund balance:		
Balance June 30, 1966	\$3,595,756	
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year (see Exhibit II)	<u>1,175,198</u>	
Balance June 30, 1967 (Note)		<u>2,420,558</u>
		<u><u>\$3,405,915</u></u>

NOTE

The Ford Foundation has adopted a policy of paying certain grants in quarterly instalments. A quarterly instalment of \$250,000 for the year ended June 30, 1968 was received on May 29, 1967. The annual instalment of \$1,000,000 for the year ending June 30, 1967 was received on June 14, 1966. The terms of the Grant from The Ford Foundation provide that \$200,000 annually is earmarked to assist the Council "to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel." At June 30, 1967 \$425,000 of the Fund balance is earmarked for this purpose. Also \$249,968 has been appropriated for other specific grants and contracts and \$25,000 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts to be made at his discretion.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1967

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council administered projects (see Exhibit III)	\$1,124,389	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see Exhibit III)	<u>45,785</u>	\$1,078,604
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	\$ 134,427	
Rent	10,850	
Professional services	7,202	
Travel and meetings	10,997	
Furniture and equipment	1,175	
Printing and duplication	8,671	
Office and other expenses	<u>9,302</u>	<u>182,624</u>
		\$1,261,228

INCOME

From investments	<u>86,030</u>
Expenditures less income	<u>\$1,175,198</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1967

	Payable June 30, 1966	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1967
American Bibliographical Center					
For a computer program for indexing historical publications		\$ 2,000		\$ 2,000	
American Council of Learned Societies					
Review of foreign acquisitions under Public Law 480		9,500			\$ 9,500
Study of the problems and needs of research libraries		39,300		19,650	19,650
American Historical Association					
Assistance to Joint Committee on Status of the National Archives		2,500		2,500	
American Library Association					
Assistance in establishing a quarterly Journal of Information Science and Library Automation		21,009			21,009
A study of systems of public libraries	\$ 50,460	2,000		52,460	
Development of guidelines for book purchasing procedures and for determining qualifications of library book vendors bidding on contracts		21,593		21,593	
Exploration of library manpower shortage problem		5,000		5,000	
Library Technology Project (Program)					
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1965			\$ 1,930	(1,930)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965	7,500		2,403	(2,403)	7,500
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1966			18,869	(18,869)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1966	21,646		10,847	10,799	
Extension of Library Technology Program to August 31, 1967	105,829			105,829	
Projects of testing and standardization to August 31, 1967	162,503			10,000	152,503
Extension of Library Technology Program to August 31, 1968		96,200			96,200
Publication of a book-selection service (Choice) at the college library level		108,855		32,880	75,975
Arizona State University					
Next steps toward implementation of the findings of the Arizona Library Survey		5,000		5,000	
Association of Research Libraries					
Development of programs for the preservation of library materials			1,740	(1,740)	
First (pilot) phase in a National Preservation Program for research library materials		26,800		26,800	
Association of Universities and Colleges of Canada					
Study to provide guidelines for development of resources and services of academic libraries in Canada		20,000		20,000	

Exhibit III

	Payable June 30, 1966	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1967
Baltimore County Public Library					
Card catalog vs. book catalog — cost and service comparisons		\$ 1,310		\$ 1,310	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to the preservation of books and other library materials	\$ 98,455	85,734		80,784	\$103,405
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	9,070				9,070
Edward A. Chapman and Paul L. St. Pierre					
Preparation of a manual on systems analysis and design as related to library operations		4,470		4,470	
Columbia University					
Operations analysis of a university research library			\$ 5,940	(5,940)	
Council of National Library Associations, Inc.					
Program development	894		517	377	
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature*	2,116			289	1,827
Georgetown University					
A feasibility study for a joint computer center for five Washington, D. C. university libraries		7,394		7,394	
Houston Fearless Corporation					
Field test of camera-processor at University of California, Los Angeles	7,443			7,443	
Indiana University Foundation					
Assistance to "A directory of Victorian periodical literature, 1824-1900; a feasibility study"		2,000		2,000	
Compilation of cases in library management		12,000		12,000	
XXVII International Congress of Orientalists (Association for Asian Studies, fiscal agent)					
Program on library resources for Oriental studies		17,500		17,500	
International Council on Archives					
Implementation of the resolutions of the Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives, Washington, May 1966		17,200		8,600	8,600
International Micrographic Congress					
Preparation and publication of an International Guide to Microfilm Equipment	3,000			3,000	
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials					
Study of the effectiveness of New Serial Titles of libraries in the United States and Canada as a continuing record of serial holdings		9,500		9,500	
Joint Libraries Committee on Copyright*					
Legal counsel for the Joint Libraries Committee on Copyright		6,664		6,664	
Library of Congress					
Establishment of a center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying	50,200			25,100	25,100
Establishment of a revolving fund to facilitate the sale of machine-readable cataloging records and information		2,000		2,000	

* Council-administered project

Exhibit III

	Payable June 30, 1966	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1967
Investigation of feasibility of automating the catalog of the Archive of American Folk Song		\$ 3,000		\$ 3,000	
Next steps to commencement of distribution of Library of Congress cataloging information in machine-readable form (Project MARC)	\$ 32,500			32,500	
Support of the work of the Federal Library Committee (supplement)	65,100			32,550	\$ 32,550
To expedite publication of the MARC Pilot Project Report		2,000		2,000	
Los Angeles County Public Library Investigation of the use of optical character recognition equipment in library operations ..	19,000			9,000	10,000
Massachusetts Institute of Technology Project Intrex — experiments in text access and related exploratory research		250,000		125,000	125,000
Meeting on circulation of books by mail, Sheraton Palace Hotel, San Francisco, California, June 24-25, 1967*		2,500		642	1,858
Michigan State University Cost comparison of three methods of converting bibliographical information to machine-readable form	29,911			29,911	
Mississippi Research and Development Center, Information Services Division Study of the feasibility of establishing a state-wide union catalog of library holdings in Mississippi	2,000			2,000	
Modern Language Association of America Assistance to International Conference on Bibliographic Form and Style		5,000			5,000
Preparations for computer-assisted production of MLA International Bibliography		4,800		4,800	
R. A. Morgan Company Construction and testing of a prototype of a bibliographer's camera		22,386			22,386
National Archives and Records Service Computer indexing and composition of archival/manuscript finding aids		40,000			40,000
National Book Committee, Inc. Toward solution of the library manpower shortage problem		4,500		4,500	
New England Board of Higher Education Development of a computer-based regional technical processing center for cataloging information					
Step 1 — Development of specifications for the center		45,862		45,862	
Task 1 — Development of a system for creating a file of cataloging data		62,300		62,300	
Tasks 2, 3 and 4 — Development of programs for file searching; development of programs for acquisitions processing; pilot operation of the center		100,000			100,000

* Council-administered project

Exhibit III

	Payable June 30, 1966	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1967
New York Metropolitan Reference and Research Library Agency, Inc.					
Coordination of reference-research library work in Metropolitan New York	\$ 27,000			\$ 27,000	
Pan American Union					
Planning a book selection list for Latin American university libraries			\$ 69	(69)	
Republic Aviation Division, Fairchild Hiller					
Analysis and verification program for utilizing the Micro-Vue System for reducing the cost of distribution of library materials	65,770			32,885	\$ 32,885
Society of American Archivists					
Archives in the Western World; Part I — preparation for publication		\$ 3,050		3,050	
Desmond Taylor and Raimund Matthis					
Preparation of a manual on the Library of Congress Classification		2,000		2,000	
Taylor-Merchant Corporation					
Development of a portable projector for microfiches/microfilm		500			500
University of California					
Preparation and publication of a handbook on data processing for libraries	34,249				34,249
University of California at Berkeley					
A bio-bibliographical index to the contributions published in Festschriften in the field of librarianship		6,375		6,375	
Experimentation in library application of facsimile-transmission equipment, Phase 2		9,119		9,119	
University of California at Davis					
Institute on Computer Science for Law Libraries, Davis, June 26-July 2, 1966			3,470	(3,470)	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Chicago, Graduate Library School					
Design and evaluation of treatments for deacidification of entire books		12,300		12,300	
Study of book thefts in academic libraries		5,668		5,668	
University of Illinois					
Preparation of a manual of university archival practice with respect to records of academic scientific research	10,000			5,000	5,000
University of Illinois, Graduate School of Library Science					
Assistance toward an international conference on education for librarianship		7,500		7,500	
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation	12,300	5,000		5,000	12,300
Various*					
Expenses connected with the "Laboratory"		5,000		4,096	904
	<u>\$841,546</u>	<u>\$1,124,389</u>	<u>\$45,785</u>	<u>\$942,579</u>	<u>\$977,571</u>

* Council-administered project

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the cover, is reproduced from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The picture has appeared in the Council's Third and subsequent annual reports.

The woodcut reproduced on the inside covers appears in *Notitia utraque cum Orientis tum Occidentis ultra Arcadii Honoriique Caesarum tempora . . .*, edited by Sigismund Gelenius and published by Hieronymus Froben and Nicolaus Episcopus, Basle, 1552. The woodcut, picturing various forms in which books have appeared, is attributed to Conrad Schnitt, and is taken from a copy of the folio in the Rare Book Division, Library of Congress.

The book-wheel reproduced as a frontispiece is preserved in the Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, and is shown here through the courtesy of M. Jacques Guignard, Conservateur en Chef. The wheel was once the property of a Parisian convent, and is presumed to date from the end of the sixteenth or the beginning of the seventeenth century. The photograph is by Maurice Junès, Paris.

The photographs of the various university libraries appear by courtesy of the directors of the respective university news services.

The photograph of Mr. William J. Barrow is by Wendell Powell, Richmond, Virginia.

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